

THE IMPACT OF BRANDING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR IN THE COSMETIC INDUSTRY IN DELTA STATE

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Abstract: The aim of this study is to determine the extent to which branding influences consumers' buying behaviour. The purpose of this research is to look at the variables that influence consumers buying behaviours. A well-structured questionnaire was used to gather primary data from respondents in the three senatorial districts of Delta State, which are Delta South, Delta Central, and Delta North. Selected supermarkets within specified cities of the three senatorial districts were also randomly chosen. The results of the study indicated that consumers' decisions for product brands are significantly influenced by branded product, making it the key component to take into considerations. However, there is significant relationship between the construct of branding and consumer buying behaviour. It was recommended that producers should focus more on a well branded product and strategies that would arouse buying decisions.

Keywords: Branding, Brans, Consumer Behaviour.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this era of globalization, companies are moving away from using traditional tools and techniques to more sophisticated marketing tools that will leave them to gaining competitive advantage in the market place thereby satisfying their customers in a unique way with branded products, hence there is a need to identify what the customers want, how they want it. There is a need to study the diversities among consumers and at the same time managing the behaviours and incorporating such behaviours into the scheme of things. Behaviour is a mirror in which everyone shows his or her image. Since market conditions are constantly changing, the new role of brand management as an integral part of holistic marketing which is more important than it ever was.

Thus, the importance of branding cannot be overemphasized, it is defined as the process of giving meaning to a particular organization, product or service by creating and shaping the mindset of consumers. It is what gives you fame, and finally, the future. By identifying yourself as a brand, you can communicate more deeply with customers, employees and the general public. Brands play a leading role in customer decision making. In present days, brands not only represent the name or the symbol of the company that produce products (or provide services). Nowadays consumers are so genuinely connected to brands that when they purchase any product (or utilize any service), brands so often influence their final choice.

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However, the cosmetic industry is such a lucrative venture that growing at an increasing pace. According to the guardian, 2022, the industry is gaining competitive edge as more people are now becoming aware of its benefits in the society. Such cosmetics brand includes personal care, deodorants, baby care, skin care, oral care fragrance and hair care etc.

There has been a bunch of researches attempted to examine all potential elements of branding and how it impact on consumer's buying behaviours (Butkeviciene, Stravinskiene, & Rutelione, 2008), but none has focused on how it impact on consumer buying behaviour of the cosmetics industry in Delta state. Thus this study tends to cover such area within the scope of this study.

However, the aim of this study is basically to know the magnitude to which branding impact consumer buying behaviour in the cosmetics industry in Delta State.

1.1 Statement of the problem

Many companies have developed good marketing programs for their activities in the target market, but are yet to come up with good brand that would benefit their customers at the long-run. Similarly, strong brands have the potential to generate long term and loyal customers, which would eventually lead to an increase in sales in the future. (Hess, Story and Danes, 2011).

Companies are facing wider range of competitors who offer a similar product to same customers (Kotler, 2005). In this increasable competitive market, companies are attempting to gain better position for them by becoming more customer-oriented (Hartmann, 2007). One wondering thing that consumers in making choice are merely responding to the outcome of their perception which is a function of attributes like brand name, mark, package, company-of-make etc. A point to note is the fact that most producers strongly believe that branding has a very high influence on consumer's choice (Ogbuji, 2008).

As a result of the wavering challenges that has posted companies in coming up with quality branding and benefits, the research tends to cover such gap by evaluating critically how the role of branding would impact positively in the buying behaviour of customers within the scope of this study.

1.2 Research Objectives

The general objective of this study is to know the impact of branding on consumer buying behaviour in the cosmetic industry in delta state, while the specific objectives are stated below;

- i. to know the extent to which branding impact on consumer buying behaviour
- ii. to have an overview of the factors affecting consumer buying behaviour
- iii. to reveal the relationship between branding and consumer buying behaviour

1.3 Research Question

- i. how does branding impact on consumer buying behaviour?
- ii. what are the factors affecting consumer buying behaviour?
- iii. what is the relationship between branding and consumer buying behaviour?

1.4 Scope of the Study

The scope of this study is centred on the impact of branding on consumer buying behaviour in the cosmetic industry in Delta State, Nigeria. This study is limited to branding and consumer buying behaviour as captured from literature. Buying behaviour is the dependent variable which came from previous researches.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW**Conceptual Review****Brand**

The American Marketing Association (AMA) defines a brand as a "name, term, sign, symbol or design, or a combination of them intended to identify the goods and services of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiate them from those of

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other sellers. Similarly, a brand is a name, symbol, or any feature that identifies one seller's good or service as distinct from those of other sellers. The American Marketing Association (2014).

According to Prasana Rosaline Fernandez (2009), to fully understand the potential of branding in terms of its growth in markets, marketers are more likely to identify the sources of brand meaning, understanding the meaning, and also to manage it in a fast changing environment. It also means the name, terms, letter, words, symbol, design, number, color, etc or a combination of these used to differentiate a product from its rivals. It is a name, sign, symbol or design or a combination of these included to identify the goods of one seller or group of sellers and to differentiate them from competitors"

A brand is an acronym, signal, mark or blueprint, or a combination of these, that identifies the maker or seller of a product or service. Kotler and Armstrong (2009).

The definition above is one of the most numerous descriptions of the word brand. Essentially, brand is a way of differentiating a company's good, or services, from those of its competitors **Kotler** (2009). Hestad (2013) however, elaborates by stating that "brands help consumers to make decisions.

"A Brand contains everything that makes a product more than just a product""Kapferer (2008: 155). That is it involves the emotional and mental assumptions that consumers have about brands, which increases the perceived value of a product or service (Ibid, 2008:10).

Branding

It means the act of naming or establishing brand name, brand mark or trade mark for a product in order to make consumers identify the product from its competitors in the market. It is a marketing practice in which a company creates a name, symbol or design that is easily identifiable as belonging to the company. This helps to identify a products and distinguish it from other products and services. It is also the process of creating a strong, positive perception of your company and its products in your customers mind. It therefore also makes it imperative to understand that branding is not about getting your target audience to choose over the competition but about getting your prospects to see you and only you as the only solution to their problems.

Kotler (1999) expands the concept of identity by stating that a brand is capable of conveying up to six different levels of meanings and this is known as "Six Dimensions of the Brand".

- i. **Attributes:** A brand communicates certain attributes to the minds of consumers such as prestige. Mtn promises the availability of network coverage "everywhere you go".
- ii. **Benefits:** The attributes that fortifies a products features by way of stating its benefits and makes it more attractive.
- iii. **Values:** That is the brand also represents the company's values, systems and structure.
- iv. **Culture:** The brand representing the characteristics of the target audience. The telecom organizations have all their branding activities and offerings that reflect the typical Ghanaian individual.
- v. **Personality:** The brand can project behavioral personality patterns of targeted consumers. For example, Mtn Ghana uses the famous Ghanaian musician, Samini as their brand ambassador.
- vi. **User:** The brand, at certain times emulates the final user.

Impact of Branding on Consumer Behaviour

A Consumer's behavior may be either positive or negative, depending on the outcome of their learning and evaluating process. The evaluation of consumer attitudes towards brands has quickly become a major part in conducting marketing research. The development of positive attitudes towards brands can lead to not only the sustaining of competitive advantage, but in the bettering of the financial health of a company. Branding has been found to be a key in formation of positive attitudes towards products, especially those involving low-levels of consumer involvement. However it has been noted that there are factors that might negate the effects of the formation of positive attitudes. One being that the effects of positive attitudes can dissipate should the consumer not purchase the product within a certain timeframe. Another factor that might negate the effects of positive attitudes might be an overtly high pricing policy, which might have a contrary effect to the consumer's positive attitudes towards the brand and result in a non sale.

The Concept of Consumer Behaviour

it is the study which involves how an individual or groups select, purchase, use or dispose of products, services ideas, or experience to satisfy their need and desires. (Paul & Jerry C, 2005). Consumer behaviour is the study of people, groups, or organisations and the methods they employ to choose, get, and discard commodities, opinions, or experiences in order to meet demands, as well as the impacts these techniques have on the consumer and society. It attempts to understand the decision-making processes of buyers, both individually and in groups. It studies characteristics of individual consumers such as demographics and behavioural variables in an attempt to understand people's wants. It also tries to assess influences on the consumer from groups such as family, friends, reference groups, and society in general.

Consumer behavior refers to the mental and emotional process and the observable behavior of consumers during searching, purchasing and post consumption of a product or service. It involves study of how people buy, what they buy, when they buy and why they buy. It blends the elements from psychology, sociology, socio psychology, anthropology and economics. It also tries to assess the influence on the consumer from groups such as family, friends, reference groups and society in general. There are several factors affecting consumer buying behavior, which can be broadly classified as:-

Social Factors- Which refer to forces that other people exert and which affect consumers’ purchase behavior. These social factors include culture and subculture, roles and family, social class and reference groups.

Psychological Factors- Which are internal to an individual and generate forces within that influence her/his purchase behavior. The major forces include motives, perception, learning, attitude and personality.

Personal Factors- Which include those aspects that are unique to a person and influence purchase behavior. These factors include demographic factors, lifestyle, and situational factors.

Assael (2004) defines purchase behavior as the tendency to act on the object; and according to him marketers is always testing the elements of the marketing mix that may influence buying behavior, for example by testing product concepts, advertising strategy, packing or brand. Assael (2004) proposes four types of purchasing behavior along these two dimensions as shown in figure below.

	<i>High Involvement</i>	<i>Low Involvement</i>
<i>Significance difference between</i>	<i>Complex buying Behavior</i>	<i>variety seeking buying behavior</i>
<i>Few differences between</i>	<i>dissonance reducing buying behavior</i>	<i>Habitual Buying Behavior</i>

Figure 2: Consumer Buying Behavior

Source: Researcher’s own construction based on Assael (2004)

Complex buying behavior can be defined when consumers are highly involved for making a purchase decision. Complex buying behavior calls for high level of involvement on the part of the consumer. In case of high involvement, consumers distinguish salient differences among the competing brands. Consumers’ are highly involved in case of expensive and highly self-expressive products.

In **dissonance reducing buying behavior** the level of consumer involvement is also high. Consumers typically undergo dissonance reducing buying behavior in case of costly and infrequent purchase. In this type of consumer behavior the consumers find it difficult to differentiate among the brands.

Habitual Buying Behavior, consumers’ level of involvement is low. This means that consumers don’t search much information among the available brands and they don’t find significant differences among the brands. The level of consumer’s involvement is also low in case of products that are frequently purchased. Consumers do not usually seek

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information much pertaining to available brands before making purchase decision. The consumers don't assess different attributes of the available brands and make purchase decision as to which brand to buy .

In **case of variety seeking buying behavior** the level of consumer involvement is low, but consumers perceive significant differences among the brands. In variety seeking buying behavior, consumers very often switch from one brand to another. Schiffman & Kanuk (2010) and Assael (2004) mentioned that the consumer made the purchase behavior is influenced by several measurements, namely; 15

- i. **Cultural measurement**, which has the most influence and the most extensive in the behavior of consumers so that marketers need to understand the influence of culture, sub-culture, and social class of consumers;
- ii. **social measurement**, which need to be considered when designing a marketing strategy because these factors can affect consumer responses;
- iii. **personal measurements**, which consists of the age and stage of life cycle, occupation, economic situation, lifestyle, personality, and self-concept affects the consumer on what is purchased; and
- iv. **Psychological measurement**, include motivation, perception, learning and beliefs and attitudes also influence the selection of consumer purchases.

Brand Equity

Today brand equity has become one of the most important marketing concepts (Martensen and Gronholdt 2004) both in business practice as well as in academic research because marketers can gain competitive advantage through successful brands (Kim, Kim, and An 2003).

The term brand equity refers to a set of assets and liabilities associated with a brand, including its name and symbol, which could impose beneficial or detrimental effects on the values arising from the products or services **Aaker** (1991) and **Yasin et al.**(2007)

However, Brand equity is a broad concept which can be further subdivided into four main areas, namely brand loyalty, name awareness, perceived quality and brand associations, Aaker, (1991) and Keller (1998).

Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty is one of the core components of brand equity and also positively and directly affected brand equity, **Atilgan et al.** (2005). Customers are sometimes forgetful and associations towards a brand serve as a brief summary for the customers to make their purchasing decision. Associations can also be used to trigger the customers to recall their past experiences, making the customers remember the brand by heart. Second, brand associations can differentiate one brand from another. It is about brand positioning that a well-positioned brand will find it hard to be attacked by its competitors due to its uniqueness. This can make the brand unbeatable but it is quite difficult to achieve since consumer taste changes quite rapidly. Third, brand associations may include some product attributes or consumer benefits which encourage the consumers to purchase the brand. Forth, some associations can engender positive feelings. For examples, adidas slogan 'Impossible is nothing', Madonna appearance in H&M's collection advertisement can stimulate customers their positive feelings about the products. Once brand associations are constructed in a meaningful way, a vivid brand image is established. Brand image possibly affects how consumers perceive the brand and hence their purchasing behaviour. There may be products on the market with similar quality and design. However, the specific brand image attached on a product may differentiate itself from the others, contributing to its higher premium price.

Characteristics of Brand

All brands have certain characteristics and that is why some are ready to just pay premium to have them. Below are some characteristics associated with a brand.

- i. A brand is an asset or a blueprint (logo, shape, color) which is extensively and proactively protected by the company or organization through legal means.

(Derick and Brad, 2008). Every recognized brand throughout the world is protected by the law. That is the trademark with which the organization does it operation with. For example, one cannot just use the Mtn brand to do whatever he or she wishes without gaining the adequate permission to do so, failure to do so would imply facing legal consequences.

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ii. Secondly, a brand has a certain category of audience that it aims at. For example, there is Mtn „prepaid“ and postpaid for the low and high class respectively. Similarly, there is an Axe deodorant and spray specifically for the youth and the angry birds branded items for kids.

iii. The brand can also be used as collateral for financial obligations and can be traded as an asset. For example, the brand known as Manchester United was bought by the Glaziers family from the United States and has since ripped lots of revenue from it. The same can also be said for the acquisition of the Chelsea by the Russian multi-millionaire, Roman Abramovich.

iv. Brands also represent what the organization stands for. For example, the moment you see the Mc Donald’s brand, fast food marketer is pictured. The same can also be said about computer giants like Apple Dell, Compaq and so on.

Significance of a brand

A brand provides an array of importance not only to the organization but the buyer as well. It includes the following;

i. Branding helps the seller to segment markets. For example, Mtn has, mobile insurance, money transfer, internet products. A very good example is Toyota Motor Company which offers major brands like Lexus, Toyota and Scion brands, each with many sub-brands such as Prius ,Camry, Yaris, Matrix, Tundra, Land Cruiser and others (Kotler and Armstrong, 2009). Apple also has a wide range of the I phones for different pockets in the markets. Like the I 4, I4s, I5 and the new I phone 5 c.

ii. Secondly, branding helps to bring value to a product or service. Consumers do attach meanings to brands and develop brand relationships. For example, most consumers in perceive a bottle of Voltic water as a high quality product whereas the same water in an unmarked bottled would be perceived as an inferior or poor quality product.

iii. Brands enable consumers to identify products or services that might be of high benefit to them. Brands also say something about product quality or offerings. – Buyers who always purchase the same brand know that they will get the same product benefits and quality each time they buy.

Empirical Review

The concept of brand is vital and draws synergy between organizational resources (human, fixed resources, tangibles and intangibles) and the strategic objectives of the organization to achieve success among competitors. In this regard, after achieving success through branding, maintaining and managing the brands reputation becomes integral to be the market leader

Alizadeh, et al., (2014) determined Comparison of Product and Corporate Branding Strategy: a conceptual framework and concluded that competition within the free market environment has grown to become a throat cutting one and hence calls for distinctive branding in order to be easily noticed by consumers.

An Empirical Study of Starbucks Coffee in Taiwan Tu et al. (2012) indicated that organizational branding directly affects customer satisfaction. In addition, the study found that the level of customer satisfaction adequately influences customer loyalty which was supported by the findings of (Eakuru and Mat 2008; analyzed and discuss the strategic positioning of associations that can be established between a corporate brand and entities in its surrounding network such as brands, product categories, persons, places and institutions.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Type of Research

This study is an exploratory, descriptive and analytical. It basically uses both quantitative and qualitative technique to investigate the dimension of the variables under study

3.2 Research Design

The survey research design is adopted for this study and it involves the asking of respondents different questions, collecting, collating, and analyzing data which is made available for describing a huge population with respondents as units of analysis.

3.3 Area of Study

This research under study was carried out in the three senatorial districts of Delta State, which are Delta South, Delta Central and Delta North, while a selected cosmetic shops were randomly picked in the said three senatorial districts of Delta State for the study.

3.4 Sample Size Determination and Sampling Techniques

The study engaged 120 sample size of respondents drawn from across major cities of Asaba, Ughelli and Oleh covering the three zones of the state senatorial district, while the basic reason is to find out opinion of respondents regarding product branding and consumer behaviour. While the random sampling technique was employed to collect data.

3.5 Research Instrument

A well structured questionnaire was prepared on a five-point Likert scale that started from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The section A encapsulated the introductory part while section B contains questions on the profile of the respondents. The last part which is section C contains close-ended questions that provided answers to the broad objectives of the study.

3.6 Sources of Data Collection

Data were gotten from primary and secondary sources. While the questionnaire that was administered to respondents served as the primary source. Moreso, Extant literature, journals, and research findings made up the secondary source.

3.7 Data Collection

Data were collected in the Ughelli, Asaba and Oleh major supermarkets covering the scope of this study respectively through the use of questionnaire. Total of 170 questionnaires were distributed from which 120 are valid and were selected for the analysis.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Demographic Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	25	28.83%
	Female	95	79.16%
Age	Below 18 years	4	3.333%
	18 – 30 years	35	29.16%
	31 – 39 years	45	37.5%
	40 – 49 years	20	16.66%
	50 above	16	13.33%
Education	SSLC	2	1.666%
	SSCE	18	15%
	Degree	45	37.5%
	Others	55	45.83%
Monthly Income	Less than 10,000	6	5%
	10,000-20,000	14	11.66%
	20,000-30,000	28	23.33%
	30,000-40,000	34	28.33%
	40,000 above	38	31.66%
Occupation	Govt Employees	39	32.5%
	Private Employees	50	41.66%
	Others	24	20%
	Students	7	5.83%

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it showed that between 120 respondents, about 25 are males represented by 28.83% while 95 were females represented by 79.16%. This showed that majority of the respondents were females, meaning those who were influenced by branding.

It was also showed that between the age brackets of 18 and 50 years above about 50 within the age bracket of 31-39 years representing 37.05% were also influenced by branding while leaving the age bracket of below 18 years at the minimal of 4 representing 3.33%.

The above table also showed that other certificate holders has the highest preference of 55 represented by 45.83% while among SSLC of 2 represented by 1.66% has the lowest preference for branding.

Between the income earners, respondents who earn #40,000 and above represented by 31.66% has the highest income earnings for branded products while earners less than 10,000 has the lowest preference for branded products represented by 6(5%).

It was also captured that within the occupation level, private employees in the employment level has the highest frequency of purchase of packaging of 50 represented by 41.66% while students with side hustle and part-time jobs were 7 represented by 5.83% which is the lowest in the occupation portfolio.

Table 2: Showing the frequency of cosmetic products purchased

Gender	Very often	Often	Rare
Male	45	55	50
Female	75	65	70
Total	120	120	120

Source: primary data

From the table above, it was observed that 75 representing 62.5% of female patronise branded products very often unlike the male counterpart. More so, 65 female respondents buy the products in an often way while 70 of the female rarely buy the branded products unlike the male respondents that patronise the products.

Table 3: Showing how customers find out or got to discover about cosmetic brands

Consumer behaviour	No	Yes	Total
Agree	20	25	45
Disagree	05	10	15
Neutral	15	10	25
Strongly Agree	25	10	35
Grand Total	65	55	120

Source: primary data

The research conducted showed that the use of the following; word of mouth, searching the internet, social media, print media and TV commercial greatly helped the firms brand to be known in different location, showing that consumers preference for the brand sharpened their buying behaviour.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

From the above study conducted, the influence of brand image, loyalty, etc on Consumer Decision Making greatly impact on consumer behaviours towards the firm’s brand.

The finding of this study also highlighted and identified the marketing opportunities by digesting the consumer decision making. It’s more likely to know what the customer is undergoing before deciding on the purchase of cosmetic products.

It was recommended that the continuous development of branding might also be an interesting area of consideration. Similarly, Policy makers have to consider branding as an important aspect of marketing to enhance a product. Other marketing concepts like pricing, promotions can also be researched into.

REFERENCES

- [1] Assael, H. (2004). *Consumer Behavior - A Strategic Approach*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin
- [2] Alizadeh, A. Moshabaki, A. Hoseini, H. K. S.& Naiej, K. A. (2014). The Comparison of Product and Corporate Branding Strategy: a conceptual framework. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, Volume 16, Issue 1. Ver. IV (Jan. 2014),
- [3] Aaker, D. A (1991). *Managing brand equity*. New York: Macmillan.
- [4] Eakuru, K. & Mat, L. (2008) Study of Attributes that Form Marketing Image of Financial Institution. *Innovative Marketing*, Volume 1, Issue 1.
- [5] Hartmann & Apaolaza, *Managing customer Loyalty in Liberalized Residential Energy Markets: The impact of Energy Branding Energy Policy Vol 35 (2007) p.2661*
- [6] Kotler, Wong, Saunders, Armstrong. (2005) *Principle of Marketing*, Fourth European edition, Financial time Prentice Hall, 2005
- [7] Kotler, P., Keller, K.L., Brandy, M., Goodman, M. & Hansen, T. 2009 *Marketing Management* Pearson Education Limited. Essex (UK) Bennett, P.D. 1995
- [8] Kotler and Armstrong, 2009. *Principles of marketing*. 13th Ed
- [9] <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352819844>
- [10] NEYATI. . A., (2015) Effect of Branding On Consumer Buying Behaviour: A Study in Relation to Fashion Industry *International Journal of Research in Humanities & Social Sciences* Vol. 3, Issue: 2, February: 2015 ISSN:(P) 2347-5404 ISSN:(O)2320 771X
- [11] Yasin, N. M., Noor, M. N. & Mohamad, O. (2007). Does image of country-of-origin matter to brand equity?. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 16 (1), 38-48